

12 On Discrete Euclidean Space

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The paper is the twelfth post of the blog “Discrete Euclidean Space” at <https://www.conceptualframeworks.org>. The post is an introduction to describe the cause behind circular motion in discrete space.

Orbital motion

In phenomenological physics every observable phenomenon is thought to exist on its own. It means that the properties of the phenomenon are part of the concept that the observable phenomenon represents. However, the equivalence of mass and energy ($E = m c^2$) shows that the properties of the phenomenon are not absolute.

There are not only “tangible” phenomena – like particles – there are also concepts that envelope one or more phenomena although the phenomenon is not the concept itself. For example, circular motion.

We know there is circular motion in the microcosm (e.g. spin, the motion of electrons around a nucleus and bounded atoms around a virtual point) and in the macrocosm (e.g. the orbits of planets around a star and stars around the centre of a galaxy). It is not really helpful to propose that the circular motion of all these observable phenomena are properties that are caused by the individual phenomena.

Circular motion seems to be a basic property of the structure of space itself, observable at every scale size. That is why the effects of circular motion – like the centrifugal force – cannot be an “independent” force.

figure 1

Figure 1 shows the change of the direction of the quanta during the concentration of energy in vacuum space. The image isn't wrong but the use of the arrows create the illusion that a quantum can move all along a trajectory.

The concept of discrete space – and modern quantum field theory – is based on the hypothesis that observable phenomena are local “excitations” of the underlying (field) structure. The structure itself is in rest and the phenomena are local variables that pass on between the units of the structure. An exchange of variable properties between 2 or more adjacent units of discrete space (the schematic structure in figure 1).

figure 2

Cosmic Microwave Background radiation

The discovery of the CMB radiation was related to the Big Bang hypothesis that describes the origin of the universe. Because when the universe cooled enough, protons and electrons will be combined to form neutral hydrogen atoms (the process of the combination of charged electrons and protons). Figure 2 shows the CMB radiation map.^[1]

If we zoom in on the CMB radiation and measure the polarization of the radiation it shows that large regions of Hydrogen gas in the early universe were polarized by gravitation (figure 3).^[2] An observation that violates the Standard Cosmological Model but is in line with the determined existence of *primordial black holes*.^[3] These type of massive black holes are in the centre of observed “full grown” extremely active galaxies some 670 million years after the hypothetical start of our universe.^{[4][5]} But ≈ 670 million years are not enough to create “full grown” galaxies with an enormous black hole in the centre of the galaxy. That is

why we have to conclude that these primordial black holes must have existed before the start of the evolution of the galaxies. Moreover, the polarization of the radiation of the early Hydrogen atoms by *gravitational* fields makes clear that in the early universe primordial black holes emerged out of vacuum space before the creation of Hydrogen atoms started.

figure 3

The creation of primordial black holes before the creation of Hydrogen atoms proves that the hypothesis about the existence of Dark energy is the result of the not-linear decrease of the average amplitudes of the non-local electromagnetic field. A non-linear decrease of amplitudes that influences the amplitudes of electromagnetic waves in vacuum space, the cause behind the red shift of the light of distant galaxies. A decrease of amplitudes that is caused by the creation of concentrations of energy like primordial black holes, matter and Dark matter (volumes of concentrated energy by the electric field without rest mass).

It also shows that the creation of Hydrogen atoms didn't result in a continuous increase of the size of the primordial black holes because of an avalanche of "incoming" Hydrogen atoms, forced by the enormous gravitational field of the primordial black holes.

figure 4

Diagram 4 shows the decrease of the amplitudes of vacuum space (green arrow) because of the local concentrations of energy (blue arrow). The volume of the universe is invariant and the dynamical surface area too, in line with

the law of conservation of energy. In other words, the creation of primordial black holes must have influenced the amplitudes of vacuum space. But not only the amplitudes itself, also the direction of the transfer because the low velocity of the black holes influences the transfer of quanta in vacuum space around. An influence that must be the origin of the observable universe where nebula and stars are rotating around enormous black holes and all these galaxies seem to have the same direction of rotation as the primordial black hole in the centre.

Electromagnetic amplitudes

The direction of the transfer of a quantum is determined by the local scalar vectors, the corresponding magnetic field. All the transfer of the fixed amount of topological deformation – the quanta – is conserved. But because the scalar vectors of the magnetic field are corresponding with the local changes of the electric field all the scalar vectors in a universe without rest mass are conserved too.

Nevertheless, the creation of rest mass – matter – is the origin of the scalar vectors of Newtonian gravity. Local scalars of the flat Higgs field that are forced to decrease their magnitude don't transfer vectors.

The consequence is that the conservation of all the scalar vectors in the universe is the conservation of the scalar vectors of the magnetic field and the field of Newtonian gravity together. Because the magnitude of the vectors of Newtonian gravity are equivalent to the "missing" vectors of the electric field, caused by the creation of rest mass.

Figure 5 shows a galaxy in the centre and the enormous volume around the galaxy where all the concentrated energy of the galaxy originates from. The black arrows represent in a schematic way the push force of the electric field – concentrating quanta at the macroscopic scale – and the blue arrows represent the scalar vectors of Newtonian gravity, pointing towards the rest mass of the galaxy in the centre of the image. The average scalar vectors of the magnetic field are not drawn in figure 5.

If there exist no magnetic field the influence of the force of concentration of the electric field can be compared with concentric shells of an enormous sphere (red circles). That means that we can determine the influence of each shell on the 2 adjacent shells at the outside and inside by relating the size of the surface areas. The result will be a diagram like figure 6. The diagram shows that the influence weakens while the radius increases.

figure 5

Figure 6 questions whether figure 1 represents a realistic impression of the direction of the quanta transfer in vacuum space around a concentration of energy at a certain moment. However, the question is not about the change of direction of quanta during the process of concentration. It is about the evolution of the geometrical configuration of the electric field in vacuum space because of the existence of a concentration of energy.

figure 6

Therefore, if the evolution of a concentration of energy has come to an end, how much will the concentration of energy still influence the geometrical configuration of the electromagnetic field within vacuum space around? Actually the electromagnetic amplitudes. Will the “vortex-like” configuration in figure 1 disappear?

It is impossible to answer this question without the examination of the evolution of the process of the concentration of energy at the microscopic scale.

References:

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